

Microbial screening of thorium(IV) and dioxouranium(VI) chelates with oxine and phenols

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Abstract : In the present investigation synthesis, characterization of mixed ligand chelates of the type MA_2L_2 , where, $M = Th^{4+}$ and UO_2^{2+} , $A = 8$ -hydroxyquinoline (oxine) and $L =$ phenols, $H_2L^1 =$ catechol, $H_2L^2 =$ pyrogallol, $H_2L^3 = 2,3$ -dihydroxy naphthalene, $H_2L^4 = 1,5$ -dihydroxy naphthalene and $H_2L^5 = 1,7$ -dihydroxy naphthalene have been reported. Their geometry have been elucidated on the basis of elemental analyses, thermogravimetric, magnetic moments, NMR, IR and electronic spectra. A study of thermal properties has also been carried out. The antimicrobial activity of 8-hydroxyquinoline and MA_2L_2 chelates have been determined and described. All the chelates showed an effective antimicrobial activity than the free ligand.

Keywords : Dioxouranium(VI), thorium(IV), oxine, phenols.

In the present communication, synthesis, characterization and antimicrobial activity of Th^{4+} and UO_2^{2+} complexes with 8-hydroxyquinoline and bidentate ligands such as catechol, pyrogallol, 2,3-dihydroxy naphthalene, 1,5-dihydroxy naphthalene and 1,7-dihydroxy naphthalene have been studied.

Experimental

Materials : All chemicals used were A.R. grade and used directly as received. The stock solutions of metal nitrates were prepared and standardized. The N-agar and N-broth (growth media) were obtained from Hi-media. Conductivity water was used throughout the work.

Synthesis : To a stirred suspension of aqueous thorium/uranium nitrate, a clear solution of 10 mL (0.1 M) 8-hydroxyquinoline (8-HQ) and 10 mL (0.1 M) solution of phenol in ethanol was added. pH of the solution was raised to 3–4.5 using 0.1 M NaOH when precipitation of complexes occur. The greenish yellow thorium and light yellow uranium compounds that separated out were collected, washed with 50 mL of water and ethanol to remove excess metal ions and ligands, dried thoroughly by suction and then in vacuum for two hours. The complexes are soluble in DMSO.

Elemental analysis were performed with a Coleman C, H, N analyzer. The metal content was determined by

gravimetric analysis after decomposing the complexes with a mixture of concentrated hydrochloric acid, nitric acid, perchloric acid and sulfuric acid in 5 : 2 : 3 : 2 mL, ratio respectively. Magnetic susceptibilities were measured by the Gouy method at 25 °C using $Hg[Co(CNS)_4]$ as calibrant. The IR spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer model 983 spectrophotometer in KBr pellets. 1H NMR spectra were determined in $DMSO-d_6$ with FT NMR spectrophotometer using TMS as an internal reference. Thermal measurements were performed using a Du Pont thermal analyzer at 10 °C min^{-1} heating rate. The electronic spectra of the complexes in DMSO solvent were measured in the range of 200–1100 nm on a Shimadzu UV-160 spectrophotometer.

Results and discussion

The analytical data of the complexes presented in Table 1 indicates 1 : 2 : 2 (MA_2L_2) stoichiometry.

Prominent IR bands in 4000–400 cm^{-1} region (KBr disc) are shown in the Table 2. The IR spectra of all the chelates is differ from ligands. The phenols showed a broad band at 2770 cm^{-1} due to intermolecular H-bonding involving the hydrogen of the phenol¹. This band is absent in chelate, indicates the replacement of hydrogen of the phenol group by metal ion. The broad band at 3300–3400 cm^{-1} is due to presence of water molecule. Some

Table 1. Analytical data and some physical properties of the metal complexes^a

Comps.	Colour	Formula weight	Yield (%) (g)	Elemental analysis (%) : Found/(Calcd.)				D.P. ^b (°C)	μ_{eff} (B.M.)
				M	C	H	N		
[ThA ₂ (L ¹) ₂].H ₂ O	Greenish	754	67	30.76	47.73	2.90	3.70	> 300	Diamagnetic
ThC ₃₀ H ₂₂ N ₂ O ₇	Yellow		(2.56)	(30.75)	(47.74)	(2.92)	(3.71)		
[ThA ₂ (L ²) ₂].H ₂ O	Greenish	784	73	29.54	45.90	2.53	3.73	> 300	Diamagnetic
ThC ₃₀ H ₂₀ N ₂ O ₉	Yellow		(2.86)	(29.59)	(45.91)	(2.55)	(3.75)		
[UO ₂ A ₂ (L ³) ₂].H ₂ O	Red	892	67	26.68	51.12	2.91	3.13	> 300	Diamagnetic
UC ₃₈ H ₂₆ N ₂ O ₉			(2.56)	(26.58)	(51.10)	(2.89)	(3.10)		
[UC ₂ A ₂ (L ⁴) ₂].H ₂ O	Blackish	892	67	26.68	51.12	2.91	3.13	> 300	Diamagnetic
UC ₃₈ H ₂₆ N ₂ O ₉	Brown		(2.56)	(26.62)	(51.07)	(2.88)	(3.08)		
[UC ₂ A ₂ (L ⁵) ₂].H ₂ O	Blackish	892	67	26.68	51.12	2.91	3.13	> 350	Diamagnetic
UC ₃₈ H ₂₆ N ₂ O ₉	Brown		(2.56)	(26.61)	(51.09)	(2.90)	(3.05)		

^aA = oxine; L¹ = catechol dianion; L² = pyrogallol dianion; L³ = 2,3-dihydroxy naphthalene dianion; L⁴ = 1,5-dihydroxy naphthalene dianion; L⁵ = 1,7-dihydroxy naphthalene dianion; ^bdecomposition point.

Table 2. Infrared spectra of the ligand and its metal complexes (cm⁻¹)^a

Comps.	$\nu(\text{O-H})$	$\nu(\text{C-H})$	$\nu(\text{C=C})$	$\nu(\text{C=N})$	$\nu(\text{M-N})$	$\nu(\text{M-O})$
A	3370b	3065b	1595m	1635m	-	-
[ThA ₂ (L ¹) ₂].H ₂ O	3330b	3050b	1590	1620m	505s	455s
[ThA ₂ (L ²) ₂].H ₂ O	3335b	3055b	1585	1615m	510s	460s
[UO ₂ A ₂ (L ³) ₂].H ₂ O	3350b	3045b	1575	1605m	500s	455s
[UO ₂ A ₂ (L ⁴) ₂].H ₂ O	3355b	3040b	1580	1610m	515s	450s
[UO ₂ A ₂ (L ⁵) ₂].H ₂ O	3340b	3060b	1580	1630m	500s	455s

^ab = broad, m = medium, s = strong; A = oxine; L¹ = catechol dianion; L² = pyrogallol dianion; L³ = 2,3-dihydroxy naphthalene dianion; L⁴ = 1,5-dihydroxy naphthalene dianion; L⁵ = 1,7-dihydroxy naphthalene dianion.

additional bands at 680 and 690 cm⁻¹ are observed due to M-OH₂². The $\nu(\text{C=N})$ band of 8-hydroxyquinoline (8-HQ) appears at 1635 cm⁻¹. This band shifts to higher energy by 15–20 cm⁻¹ indicates the coordination of nitrogen of 8-HQ³. The $\nu(\text{C-O})$ at 1220–1230 cm⁻¹ in phenol disappears at 1240–1230 in chelate, is convincing proof of coordination of metal with secondary ligands in all the complexes. The complexes also show bands at 450–465 cm⁻¹ and 580–560 cm⁻¹, which may be assigned to $\nu(\text{M-O})$ and $\nu(\text{M-O-C})$, respectively⁴. The bands at 450–554 cm⁻¹ corresponds to $\nu(\text{M-N})$ stretching in all the chelates⁵.

The geometry of the synthesized complexes is proposed on the basis of electronic spectra and magnetic moments. The Th^{IV} and UO₂^{VI} complexes are diamagnetic in

nature⁶. The bands at 27600 and 27300 cm⁻¹ for Th^{IV} complexes and 30864, 33222 and 32786 for UO₂^{VI} complexes with catechol, pyrogallol, 2,3-dihydroxy naphthalene, 1,5-dihydroxy naphthalene and 1,7-dihydroxy naphthalene, respectively, are due to ligands. The band at 31100 cm⁻¹ may be due to charge transfer transition or may be due to $n \rightarrow \pi^*$ $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ ⁷. The above spectral studies are favourable for the suggested geometry of Th^{IV} and UO₂^{VI} complexes.

From the TGA study it has been observed that the presence of water molecule is a water of crystallization in both the metal complexes.

Antimicrobial activity :

Antimicrobial activity has been determined same as done earlier and data has been presented in Table 3.

Table 3. Antimicrobial activity of the ligand and its metal complexes evaluated by minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC; $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$)

Ligand/Complexes	Microbial species			
	Bacterial			Yeast
	<i>E. coli</i>	<i>B. subtilis</i>	<i>S. aureus</i>	<i>S. cerevisiae</i>
A	+	+	+	+
[ThA ₂ (L ¹) ₂].H ₂ O	+++	++	++	+++
[ThA ₂ (L ²) ₂].H ₂ O	+++	++	++	+++
[ThA ₂ (L ³) ₂].H ₂ O	+++	++	++	+++
[ThA ₂ (L ⁴) ₂].H ₂ O	+++	++	++	+++
[ThA ₂ (L ⁵) ₂].H ₂ O	+++	++	++	+++
[UO ₂ A ₂ (L ¹) ₂].H ₂ O	+++	++	++	+++
[UO ₂ A ₂ (L ²) ₂].H ₂ O	+++	++	++	+++
[UO ₂ A ₂ (L ³) ₂].H ₂ O	+++	++	++	+++
[UO ₂ A ₂ (L ⁴) ₂].H ₂ O	+++	++	++	+++
[UO ₂ A ₂ (L ⁵) ₂].H ₂ O	+++	++	++	+++

A = 8-Hydroxyquinoline; H₂L¹ = catechol; H₂L² = pyrogallol; H₂L³ = 2,3-dihydroxy naphthalene dianion; H₂L⁴ = 1,5-dihydroxy naphthalene dianion and H₂L⁵ = 1,7-dihydroxy naphthalene dianion.

Inhibition diameter in mm (% inhibition) : +, 6–10 (27–45%); ++, 10–14 (45–64%); +++, 14–18 (64–82%); +++++, 18–22 (82–100%). Percent inhibition values are relative to inhibition (22 mm) with 100% inhibition; —, No inhibition.

Conclusion :

From elemental analyses, IR, thermogravimetric analyses, UV-visible spectra, ¹H NMR spectra and magnetic moment, the proposed geometries of the

complexes are established. All the complexes of Th^{IV} and UO₂^{VI} with 8-HQ and phenol shows significant antimicrobial activity compared to free ligand, hence these complexes are very important in medical and biochemical sciences.

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